
Intellectual Property Rights in Commerce

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.14958890

Abstract:

The property which designates those things that are commonly recognized as being the possessions of an individual or a group of persons, property right of ownership is associated with property that establishes the goods as being ones own thing in relation to other individuals or groups of person. Assuring the owner the property right to dispense with the property in a manner he or she deems fit, whether to use or not use, exclude others from using or to transfer ownership to other.

Properties or assets are of two types tangible property and intangible property. one that is in physical form and the other which is not in any physical form Land, building, farm, car, cash money, jewellery, objects which has length, width, height are tangible property. Intellectual property is one of the forms of intangible property which commands a material value which can also be higher than the value of a tangible property patent, trademark, copyright, geographical indication, industrial design, trade secret, plant variety and farmers protection right, lay out design and integrated circuit are intellectual properties.

Keywords: *IPR, Commerce, e-commerce.*

Introduction:

Intellectual Property Right is a right which protect creations of mind, like invention, designs, slogan, logo, picture, new composition in music, literature, draft, song etc. It give some of the exclusive rights to inventor .it provide incentive to the individual for new creations .it gives recognition to the creators and inventors. It provides incentive for research, research to revenue. Patent is one of intellectual property, inventor make an object which is new, non-obvious and industrial utility Copyright is intellectual property right given by the law to creators of literary, dramatic, book, pictures, musical and artistic works, software, software applications.

Trademark is intellectual property

rights which protect logos, sounds, words, colours, symbols used to distinguish products which are used in service sector. Trade secret is intellectual property rights which protect confidential information on which business grows and stand. Patent, trademark, copyright, geographical indication, industrial design, trade secret, intellectual property in accordance with business point of view.

Importance:

- Intellectual property rights provide recognition to creator and inventor.
- IPR provides incentive for research to researcher.
- IPR provides exclusive rights to inventor.

- IPR ensures the availability of the genuine and original products.
- IPR avoids duplication of product and justifies inventor's efforts.

Objectives:

1. To create public awareness about IPR and social, economic and cultural benefits of IPR among all sectors.
2. To promote for economic growth.
3. To avoid duplication of product.

Description:

Intellectual property rights are the rights given to persons over the creations of their minds. They usually give the creator an exclusive right over the use of his/her creation for a certain period of time. Various IPRs used in business and commerce such as patents, trademark, trade secrets, industrial design, copyrights, Geographical indication.

IPR are very important in commerce for the protection of creations like inventions, designs, trademarks, trade secrets, matters. IPR helps in business, service sectors for growth, development and hold stability in marketplace.

Patents protect inventions that meet criteria such as novelty, non-obviousness, industrial utility. Copyrights protect words, sound, logos, slogans, books, software applications, music, literature, image and symbol. Trademark protects symbols, logos, words, colors. Industrial Design protects as parts of machine, ornaments. Trade secrets protect confidential information such as process, configuration, composition, ingredients. Geographical indication protects matter with reference to its occurrence, location and speciality.

Intellectual property refers to creation of the mind, inventions, literacy

and artistic works, symbols, images, names, logos slogan used in commerce. In digital age Businessman are often unaware about their business assets, to run business smoothly. Depending on business, assets are Land, location, building, furniture, computer, equipments, electricity, vehicles, investments, man power, licenses, stocks, cash, supplies, goodwill, intangible intellectual properties trademark, trade secrets, copyright, industrial design, Geographical indication.

IPR is a highly valuable component of commerce, e-commerce. IPR stands for the rights that allow a business to use their invention to gain financial benefits and market leadership, over its competitors.

Intellectual property right plays a crucial role in the field of e-commerce in digital age. IPR is a highly valuable component of e-commerce. Despite its significant value, it is often neglected because most people fail to understand it and because its connections to e-commerce are not very obvious, regardless, IP and e-commerce are entirely interdependent e-commerce typically involves selling products or services based on Intellectual Property and its licensing. In the digital world, there are so many types of Intellectual Properties that can be traded through e-commerce platform like music, photographs, designs, pictures, software, content, slogans, logos, secrets and so much more. In all these scenarios, IPR is especially significant since the value of these goods need to be protected. The protection is afforded through tools such as Intellectual Property laws and technological security systems IPR infringement. If IP theft is rampant, it could potentially runs an e-commerce business which is IPR in e-commerce is extremely crucial. The role of Intellectual property Right law in e-commerce is most clearly visible in today's online and

digital economy. The presence of practices and statutes that govern the functioning of IP laws. IP Laws encourages new creations and protecting the hard work put in by the creator. The IP law prevents others work from stealing IPs and using it to their financial benefits without paying the creator for the work they put in, and their invention.

Need of IPR in commerce:

Intellectual property Rights protects innovation, process, product, soft application, logos, for well-being of humanity and capacity to create and invent new work in the areas of technology and culture.

Encourages inventor for innovation:

The legal protection to creator for new creations, encourages the commitment of additional resources for further innovation.

Economic growth: The promotion and protection of IP gives spurs for economic growth, creates new jobs and industries and enhance the quality and enjoyment of life.

Safeguard the rights of creators: IPR is required to safeguard for creators and other producers of their intellectual commodity, goods and services by granting them certain time, limited rights to control the use made of the manufactured goods.

Encourage for self- employability or start-up: It promotes innovation and creativity and ensures ease of doing business.

Develop entrepreneurship: It promotes enterprises and open self owner business which creates employable farms.

Facilitates the transfer of technology: Fascination of knowledge and technology in the form of foreign direct investment, joint ventures and licensing.

IPR infringement: When third party uses registered IP without permission of

inventor's right is to make legal legislation law against third party

Provide Safety: It provides guarantees regarding the quality and safety of genuine products made by the original manufacturer and avoid duplication

Trade and Economic Security: It provides trading and economic security in business, loyalty, trust so as to grow business.

Provide e-commerce security: It provides information about company, logos, originality about product and service through website to customer in online shopping

Types of IPR protection in e-Commerce:

Intellectual Property is most valuable asset. Patents and Trademarks that help enhance the value of business. In today's digital age patent and trademark are not sufficient to run business smoothly, with originality. Trusty e-commerce needs some technology such as **Neighbouring rights Database rights, trade name law.** Intellectual property law protect work, consumers trust. IP provide safe and authentic products and service to customer.

Patents: Patents protect an invention or a technical product or process. It is unlawful for others to make, use, resell, rent out, or supply the patented object or process. The patent holder may however give others permission to do so by granting a Patent licence.

Copyright: Copyright protects works of literature, scholarship, science and art. These include books, films, paintings, music, games, photographs and software. Copyright is regulated by the Copyright Act. Copyright exists automatically, so there is no need to register or apply for it. Anyone who makes a drawing at their desk at home automatically owns the copyright to it.

Neighbouring rights or Relate right (Netherland country IPR Act):

These rights protect the work of performers, music and film producers, and broadcasting companies. This protection is closely related to that offered by copyright, Like copyright, these rights arise automatically, as is laid down in the Neighbouring Right Act.

Trademarks: Entrepreneurs can use a trademark to distinguish their products or services from other products and services. Trademark rights protect the names of products or services. They also protect a product's logo and the design of its packaging. Entrepreneurs must register matters trademark to protect it.

Design rights: Design rights protect the appearance of two or three-dimensional products. These include wallpaper patterns, textiles and the design of household items such as alarm clocks, toys and chairs, bottle, ornaments protected by design right which must be new.

Database rights (Netherland Act): Databases consisting of collections of ordered data of any company or government confidential data may be protected by database rights. Confidential data such as official publication and statistical data. Building up such a database often requires a considerable investment of time and money. That is why the producers of databases are protected by the Database Act.

Trade name law: Trade name law protects the name under which an enterprise does business. A tradename comes into being automatically as soon as the enterprise starts operating. The owner does not have to register the tradename in the commercial

register. The protection of trade names is regulated in the Trade name Act.

Plant breeders' right: Plant breeders can invoke plant breeds right to protect their new plant varieties. These new varieties frequently result from long and costly breeding processes. The Board for Plant Varieties is responsible for granting plant breeders' rights.

Semiconductor topography rights (chip right): Semiconductor topography rights. Protect the design of electronic circuits on computer chips These rights protect circuits designed to perform specific functions.

Conclusion:

1. Intellectual Property is its most valuable asset that helps enhance the value of their business intellectual property law protect their work, consumers trust Intellectual Property provide them safe and authentic products.
2. IPR in e-commerce helps protect businesses that operate on online platforms. Since the online retail space is growing at an exponential rate.
3. Intellectual Property Rights help companies safeguard and maintain their secret trade activities.
4. IP rights in e-commerce allow owners to claim a share of the company's profits.
5. IPR in e-commerce protects activities in the e-commerce field.

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